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Deliverable D6.4

A screenshot of an OER Commons page. The header includes the OER Commons logo and navigation links: Discover, Hubs, Groups, Our Services, and Add OER. A sidebar on the left contains icons for Save, Rate, Download, Share, Google Classroom, Print, Standard Alignment, and a menu icon. The main content area displays the title "2020 Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather" with a "Student View (Opens in new window)" link. Below the title is a slide navigation indicator showing "1 of 3" and a "Next" button. The slide content features the title "Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather" in red text above a satellite image of a tropical cyclone. A second "1 of 3" and "Next" indicator is visible below the slide.

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<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1 Abstract /publishable summary

ESiWACE2 WP6 offers the following trainings on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools applied to the domain of weather and climate modelling: I/O, DSL, C++, code coupling, data analytics and containerisation. Two summer schools, including presentations and hands-on on these trainings, were also organised in August 2020 and 2021.

For all trainings, online digital media was created as Open Educational Resources (OER) material (<https://www.oercommons.org>). This material is available under permissive licences and can be used to get a general knowledge on these HPC subjects. The OER material produced for each training is presented here.

2 Conclusion & Results

OER material extracted from all ESiWACE2 trainings is now available on <https://www.oercommons.org>. These trainings constitute a first transfer of general knowledge from ESiWACE2 experts to the community. Delivering these trainings results in a larger number of scientists and engineers with higher qualifications in the use and optimisation of climate and weather applications on tier-0 machines, increasing HPC awareness in that community. Ultimately, these trainings will allow climate and weather research to be more productive, favouring European scientific excellence in that field. The OER material described can be used by students, scientists and engineers to get a general knowledge on HPC aspects covered by ESiWACE2 trainings: I/O, DSL, C++, code coupling, data analytics and containerisation.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of the following macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	X
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	X
Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	X
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	X
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

WP6 offers diverse training programmes on pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools for engineers and scientists in the domain of weather and climate modelling.

Trainings are offered in different HPC areas of ESiWACE2 expertise :

- IO -see Section 4.1
- DSL -see Section 4.2
- C++ -see Section 4.3
- code coupling software -see Section 4.4
- data analytics -see Section 4.5
- containerisation -see Section 4.6.

Two summer schools, with presentations and hands-on on all these trainings, were also organised in August 2020 and 2021 (see deliverable D6.1).

For all trainings, online digital media was created as Open Educational Resources (OER) material (<https://www.oercommons.org>). This material, presented in this document, is available under a permissive CC-BY¹, or CC BY-SA², or CC BY-NC-SA³ licence and can be used by students, scientists and engineers to get a general knowledge on HPC aspects covered by these trainings.

4.1 Input/Output and Middleware

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The OER session available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/80423> covers a 90-minute lecture and a (45+15)-minute laboratory practical. Climate and weather research is typically data-intensive and applications must utilise input/output efficiently. Often, a user struggles to assess observed performance leading to superfluous attempts to tune the application and optimise performance in the wrong layer of the stack. The content of this session is twofold. Firstly, storage layers focusing on the NetCDF middleware are discussed and a performance model that aids users to identify inefficient I/O is provided. Secondly, the NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) convention that is often used as a standard to exchange data is discussed.

The objectives of the lecture are to:

- Discuss challenges for data-driven research
- Describe the role of middleware and file formats
- Identify typical I/O performance issues and their causes
- Apply performance models to assess and optimise the application I/O performance
- Design a data model for NetCDF/CF

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- Implement an application that utilises parallel I/O to store and analyse data
- Describe ongoing research activities in high-performance storage

The laboratory helps exploring NetCDF files and utilities and the objectives are to:

- Execute programs in C that read and write NetCDF files in a metadata-aware manner
- Analyse, manipulate and visualise NetCDF data

4.2 DSL

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The OER lecture available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86681> provides an in-depth view on Domain Specific Languages (DSLs) in the weather and climate context. Two DSLs are discussed: the dusk and dawn toolchain as well as PsyClone. Both the dusk and dawn section as well as the PsyClone part contain lectures as well as hands-on exercises. The dusk and dawn lectures contain:

- Short introduction to important concepts in weather models and computational patterns in Finite Volume methods
- In-depth explanation of the dusk frontend language with a wide array of examples
- A look at integrating the DSL approach into existing code bases
- Detailed discussions on how the DSL ensures performant execution of the generated code

The hands-on sessions take the student through small numerical exercises, starting from simple differential operators up to a complete shallow water solver implemented in dusk. The PsyClone lectures contain:

- A general overview of the PsyClone toolchain followed by an in-depth look at the whole PsyClone ecosystem
- Interoperability of the PsyClone and dusk and dawn toolchains
- How PsyClone can be applied to the existing models NEMO as well as LFRIC
- A look at the different optimisations (shared and distributed memory) performed by PsyClone

All lectures as well as hands-on sessions have been recorded and are available on the ESiWACE YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4VnUf-ZZ0E200nK5M0GPmg>).

4.3 C++

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C++ is a very powerful programming language, used worldwide to develop complex and performance-critical applications. It is thus an important candidate for developing HPC applications. Mastering the power of the language requires substantial effort but pays off as projects scale up in size and complexity. As the hardware architectures become more and more diverse and complex, C++ allows the implementation of the proper abstractions to make applications sustainable in the future. Specifically, C++ allows the development of type safe, flexible and portable functionalities, with no runtime overhead.

The OER course available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/87057> has many units derived largely from our experience using C++ for HPC. It is assumed the student has a basic knowledge of C++ programming in order to put these advanced topics into a proper context. Several C++ Use Cases are provided as an illustration of how C++ can be used productively in the HPC setting. Finally, there is also a unit containing C++ exercises, which are publicly available in a repository.

- Introduction
- Values and Object Initialisation
- Name Resolution
- Templates
- Move Semantics
- Constexpr / Consteval / Constinit
- Lambdas and functions
- STL
- Ranges
- Resource Management
- Concept-based design
- Use Case: DLAF
- Use Case: GROMACS
- Use Case: Tasking library
- Use Case: Kokkos
- Q&A / Exercises

4.4 Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT

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The following material was extracted from OASIS3-MCT Small Private Online Course (see <https://cerfacs.fr/online-training/>) and is now available as OER material at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/85340>. We note that this material gives a detailed overview of the steps to follow to couple a code with OASIS3-MCT but it is strongly recommended to follow a more in-depth training, e.g. the SPOC, before attempting to achieve a comprehensive coupling in a real case.

- A general introduction on describing the OER material available (video)
- A general overview on code coupling in general and coupling using OASIS3-MCT (video)
- A presentation of the toy coupled model (video)
- Explanation on MPI communicators (video)
- Initialisation and termination (video and quiz)
- Partitioning theory (video and quiz)
- Grid data file creation (video and quiz)
- Coupling field declaration and end of definition phase (video and quiz)
- Sending and receiving the coupling fields (video and quiz)
- The LAG concept (video and quiz)

- First part of the configuration file: general coupling parameters (video and quiz)
- Second part of the configuration file (video and quiz)
- Final exam (questions + solutions)

4.5 High-Performance Data Analytics (HPDA)

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The OER material is available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86887>

A set of PDF slides concerning HPDA was prepared as OER material starting from the last HPDA & Visualisation training organised in September 2021⁴. Besides the video lectures and related slides, links to the training and hands-on material, as well as instructions for their execution are also provided.

The effective management of the increasing data volumes in many scientific domains requires analysis tools able to effectively scale with these massive datasets. The Ophidia HPDA framework, which represents an open source solution for the analysis of scientific multi-dimensional data at scale, tries to address these data challenges in order to support HPDA.

The training provides an overview of the Ophidia HPDA framework main features for climate data analysis and a practical tutorial on how to use the framework in examples of real-world analysis. It is divided into two parts.

The first section introduces the Ophidia framework, its design and the main features supported for data management and analysis. A video lecture and related slides are provided. The main aspects covered by this part are:

- Introduction to HPDA and data challenges in eScience
- Ophidia framework overview and motivations
- Main features and interaction modes provided
- Framework architecture
- Storage model, data partitioning and mapping to NetCDF file
- Data analytics operators and primitives
- Introduction to PyOphidia

The second section provides a practical walkthrough of the features provided by the framework using the PyOphidia Python module to run some data analysis applied to real climate data. A video about the practical tutorial, as well as the related slides and a listing of the examples run, are provided. The main topics covered by this part are:

- Accessing and setting up the tutorial environment
- Loading a NetCDF file
- Managing the cube virtual space
- Analysing an Ophidia datacube
- Plotting the results on a map
- Performing time series analysis

⁴<https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-2021>

4.6 Containerisation

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The OER lecture available at <https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/86725> provides an introduction to Linux containers, going from Docker on a laptop to the Sarus container engine on a large-scale supercomputer.

The lecture is composed of 3 parts:

1. Introduction to containers and Docker:
 - Video: lecture introducing general concepts about containers and Docker as a general-purpose container solution (recorded at the ESiWACE2 Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather 2021)
 - Video: Docker tutorial covering the essential commands, how to leverage CUDA and NVIDIA GPUs, and an example of packaging an MPI program into a container image (recorded at the ESiWACE2 Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather 2021)
 - PDF document: Accompanying slides
2. Docker hands-on exercises; material for revisiting and expanding in a self-paced fashion the Docker examples presented during the first part:
 - PDF document: Docker step-by-step guide
 - Video: introduction to hands-on exercises (recorded by Simon Wilson (NCAS, UK) for the ESiWACE2 Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather 2020)
3. Containers on HPC with the Sarus Container Engine:
 - Video: lecture on deploying containers with Sarus on Piz Daint (recorded at the ESiWACE2 Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather 2020)
 - PDF document: Accompanying slides

5 References

No related reference

6 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No particular difficulties were encountered when producing OER material based on the training sessions organised through ESiWACE2.

7 How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

The trainings described here and offered as OER material are essential, as running (pre-) exascale applications on the most advanced HPC platforms asks for well-trained and highly-qualified staff ensuring sound programming of the applications and expert use of all components in the ecosystem. These trainings result in a larger number of scientists and engineers with higher qualifications in the use and optimisation of climate and weather applications on tier-0 machines, increasing HPC awareness in that community. Ultimately, these trainings will allow climate and weather research to be more productive, favouring European scientific excellence in that field.

8 Sustainability

The trainings offered constitute a first transfer of general knowledge from ESiWACE2 experts to the community while the services from WP3 constitute a precise and individual answer to user specific problems encountered with their code on the path to exascale. These trainings leverage the developments done in WP1 (for OASIS3-MCT), WP2 (DSL, Containerisation), WP4 (Input/Output) and WP5 (HPDA).

These trainings are coordinated at the EU level, through the supervision of the FOCUS CoE.

9 Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We ensure the uptake of the OER material by the targeted audience through the following actions:

- The addresses for the training-related OER material are listed on the training page of ESiWACE web site (see <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/trainings>).
- The calendar of the trainings per se is published at <https://calendar.time.ly/5r0mgbac/stream> together with the trainings of the other CoEs, thanks to the coordinating FOCUS CoE.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

The training themselves were or will be delivered as follows:

Past Trainings	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo or Web Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Lucas Benedicic et al. (ETHZ) session at "Container Hackathon for Modellers"	3-5/12/2019 - Lugano (CH)	Scientific Community	https://zenodo.org/record/4323261	15
On-line course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	6-10/07 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	10
Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather	24-28/08 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/the-project/stories/summer-school	162
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2020	6,13,22 /10 and 3/11 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-2020	20
Domain-Specific Languages (DSLs) for Weather and Climate	23-27/11 2020 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/dsl-training	60
On-line course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	29/05 - 12/06 2021 (online)	Scientific Community	N/A	15
Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather	23-27/08 2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2021/esiwace-school	125
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2021	13-16/09 2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-vis-2021	20
Advanced C++ online course organised by CSCS/ETHZ	11-13/10 2021 (online)	Scientific Community	https://www.esiwace.eu/events/c-workshop	35

(1)

Planned Trainings	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo or Web Link	Estimated number of persons reached
On-line course on Code Coupling using OASIS3-MCT	Spring 2022 (on-line)	Scientific Community	N/A	planned
High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation 2022	Autumn 2022 (on-line)	Scientific Community	N/A	planned

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A